

JEWISH UNIVERSITY OF COLORADO
Department of Philosophy

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How the Sars-CoV-2 Pandemic has changed our way of teaching and learning

Abstract

In mid-March 2020, we were also caught cold with the closure of our campus due to Covid-19. Having just returned from a trip to Israel with our class of 2020, we had to quickly create structures that would make reliable distance learning possible. Now that the pandemic is coming to an end, where are we?

The situation

Training courses on digital learning were multiplied internally and technical conditions were immediately created so that students and young people could also learn and apply new knowledge successfully and interactively at their desks at home. In the meantime, students and teachers at the Jewish University of Colorado have become experienced digital learners.

We have succeeded in achieving this through the following interventions/measures:

- A high degree of willingness on the part of colleagues to engage in further training in a large network of schools who were advanced in the field of distant learning.
- Courage to break new ground and to try out and use different digital learning platforms, software and apps.
- Investment in reliable hardware and staff maintenance of the systems by hiring multiple IT technicians.
- Establishing a fixed online schedule, which ensures that the contact with our students will remain on reliable grounds.
- A high level of collegial exchange

- An optimistic attitude that always looks for new development opportunities, even in times of crisis.
- An awareness of the importance of private exchange in addition to professional gatherings.
- Daily online teaching via Zoom or Google Meet.

Of course, the new form of learning also presents us all with new challenges, but overall, very positive developments can also be observed. For example, students have taken more personal responsibility for the learning process. Learning processes and results are structured and stored securely so that they are always available. And finally, the students and young people have acquired new skills in using their computers, which have been transformed from a secondary tool into a main pillar of teaching and learning.

In a nutshell

The pandemic forced the Jewish University into a warp speed digitalization effort which led to surprisingly good results. All these developments will continue to determine and positively influence students' learning in the future.

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